

MISO Broadcasting for SWIPT with Batteryless Receivers and Battery-Constrained Self-Sustainable IRS

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Abstract

This paper considers a multiple-input single-output broadcasting system for simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) with batteryless user terminals (UT) which is aided by a self-sustainable intelligent reflecting surface (IRS). The UTs and the battery-powered IRS employ the time switching (TS) or the power splitting (PS) scheme. The various combinations of these SWIPT protocols result in different system operation modes. Considering a nonlinear energy harvesting (EH) model, we aim at jointly optimizing in each mode the transmit and reflect beamforming vectors, along with the TS or/and PS ratios, such that the transmit sum-power is minimized subject to the quality-of-service requirements of the UTs, the EH requirements of the IRS, and its battery's capacity. We formulate, whenever required, corresponding multi-objective optimization problems and convert them into equivalent single-objective optimization problems using the epsilon-constraint method. We develop iterative algorithms under the alternating minimization or block coordinate descent frameworks that utilize the semi-definite relaxation, inner approximation, and successive convex approximation methods, along with low-complexity heuristics or/and line search, to efficiently tackle the challenging non-convex optimization problems under study. Numerical simulation results highlight the performance gains of the proposed resource allocation strategies over baseline techniques and provide valuable insights.

Index Terms

Time switching (TS)-/power splitting (PS)-simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT), batteryless Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices, energy-sustainable intelligent reflecting surface (IRS), nonlinear energy harvesting (EH) model, joint transmit/reflect beamforming and TS/PS optimization, multi-objective optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, we live in the Internet-of-Things (IoT) era [1]. According to Ericsson, the number of IoT connections worldwide will reach 30.2 billion by the end of 2027, as opposed to the 14.6 billion connections in June 2022 [2]. Likewise, it is expected that the global IoT market will grow from 381.3 billion US dollars in 2021 to 1,854.76 billion US dollars in 2028 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 25,4% [3].

The use of batteryless IoT terminals is gaining popularity lately in situations where cost reduction is of utmost importance (e.g., wireless sensors) and in challenging scenarios where frequent wired charging is regarded as a cumbersome procedure (e.g., massive IoT setups and IoT networks in remote/rural areas, in hazardous environments, or in locations with restricted access) [4]. Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) has been recently proposed as a means to ensure perpetual operation of such devices. This paradigm integrates wireless power transfer (WPT) from dedicated radio frequency (RF) sources with radio communication to both achieve long-range and provide quality-of-service (QoS) guarantees, contrary to alternatives such as near-field WPT, renewable sources, and ambient RF energy harvesting [5].

Batteryless IoT terminals follow a *harvest-use* approach, where the harvested direct current (DC) energy becomes immediately available for supporting the device's operation in the current timeslot. Battery-powered IoT nodes, in turn, commonly adopt a *harvest-store-use* approach, where the harvested DC energy is buffered and becomes available for use (i.e., it replenishes the energy stored in the battery) in the next timeslot [6].

Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology leverages the spatial degrees-of-freedom of multi-antenna access points (AP) to enhance the efficiency of RF energy transfer, which is deteriorated by the distance-dependent path loss, and the information rate of the users via transmit precoding (TP) [7]. In principle, we could utilize an excess of AP antennas to further improve the performance [8]. Nevertheless, the stringent cost and energy consumption constraints of the APs in IoT setups typically prohibit the deployment of such massive MIMO systems, since each antenna is fed by its own RF chain which is an expensive and power-hungry component.

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Fig. 1. (a) System setup. (b) Operation modes.

The emerging intelligent reflecting surface (IRS) technology constitutes an alternative that resolves these issues via reflect beamforming (RB) [9], i.e., by adjusting the coefficients (amplitude/phase shift) of its passive reflecting elements to reconfigure the wireless channel.

A. Related Work and Motivation

Joint TP/RB optimization has been studied manifold in the literature in the context of IRS-aided multiple-input single-output (MISO) broadcasting for SWIPT. The work [10] considers a setup with information decoding and energy harvesting receivers (IDR/EHR) and deals with the multi-objective optimization problem (MOP) of maximizing the sum-rate and the total harvested energy. In [11], [12], the authors tackle the maximization of the minimum power or the weighted sum-power received at the EHRs, respectively, whereas [13] focuses on transmit sum-power minimization. The latter problem is revisited for a corresponding setup with power splitting (PS)-SWIPT receivers in [14]–[16] assuming imperfect channel state information (CSI), interference constraints in a spectrum underlay setting, or an analog/digital AP that employs hybrid precoding, respectively. The authors in [17] consider a time switching (TS)-SWIPT setup and maximize the minimum harvested energy and information rate.

IRSs are equipped with a large number of low-power passive reflecting elements to achieve high RB gains and compensate for the double path loss noticed over the IRS-cascaded AP–user channels. Hence, their overall power consumption is non-negligible (e.g., an IRS consisting of 100 elements with 3-bit resolution consumes 0.15 W of power [18]–[20]). This is particularly problematic for battery-powered IRS implementations, which have been recently proposed as a means to enhance the flexibility of network deployment. The use of RF-EH under SWIPT

has been proposed as a means to achieve energy-sustainable operation of such IRS nodes. Corresponding works consider sum-rate maximization in a wireless powered communication network with single-antenna nodes [21] or in a secure MISO broadcasting system [22] and capacity maximization in a single-user MISO communication system [23]. However, such designs have not been investigated in the context of IRS-aided SWIPT.

B. Objectives and Contributions

Motivated by the above, this paper considers an IRS-aided MISO broadcasting system for SWIPT where the IRS and the user terminals (UT) independently apply the TS-/PS-SWIPT protocols. We assume that the AP is linked with the UT via both direct and IRS-cascaded channels, to enable comparisons with the case where no IRS is deployed. In addition, we utilize the logistic EH model, which captures the nonlinearities of practical EH circuits [24]. We also consider continuous reflection coefficients for reduced implementation and algorithmic complexity [9] and assume availability of perfect CSI at the AP to focus on the behavior of the proposed strategies and obtain upper performance bounds. We aim at developing resource allocation strategies for each operation mode (i.e., combination of SWIPT schemes) to minimize the transmit sum-power while meeting the QoS requirements of the users, the EH requirements of the IRS, and the capacity of its battery. This work's individual contributions are listed next:

- We formulate novel MOPs to design the resource allocation strategies and convert them to equivalent single-objective optimization problems (SOP) using the ϵ -constraint method.
- We develop alternating minimization (AM) or block coordinate descent (BCD) algorithms that involve the semi-definite relaxation (SDR), inner approximation (IA), and successive convex approximation (SCA) methods to efficiently tackle the challenging non-convex optimization problems under study and computer their complexity.
- Numerical evaluations highlight the performance gains of the proposed strategies against baseline techniques and provide valuable insights.

C. Structure and Mathematical Notation

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the system model. Section III presents the problem formulations and the corresponding algorithms. Sections IV and ?? provide the numerical evaluations and our conclusions, respectively.

Notation: x : a scalar; \mathbf{x} : a column vector; \mathbf{X} : a matrix; $[\mathbf{x}]_n$: the n -th element of \mathbf{x} ; $[\mathbf{X}]_{n,m}$: the (n, m) -th entry of \mathbf{X} ; \mathbb{C}^N and $\mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$: the sets of complex-valued N -dimensional vectors and $N \times M$ matrices, respectively; \mathbb{H}^N : the set of Hermitian $N \times N$ matrices; $\|\mathbf{x}\|$: the Euclidean norm of \mathbf{x} ; \mathbf{X}^* , \mathbf{X}^\dagger , $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{X})$, $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{X})$, $\|\mathbf{X}\|_2$, and $\|\mathbf{X}\|_*$: the complex conjugate, complex conjugate transpose, trace, rank, spectral norm, and nuclear norm, respectively, of a matrix \mathbf{X} with appropriate size; $\text{diag}(\mathbf{x})$: a diagonal matrix whose main diagonal is \mathbf{x} ; $\text{Diag}(\mathbf{X})$: the main diagonal of \mathbf{X} ; $\mathbf{X} \succeq \mathbf{0}$: a positive semi-definite (PSD) matrix \mathbf{X} ; $\mathbf{0}$: the null vector of appropriate size; $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^1(\mathbf{X})$: the dominant eigenvector of \mathbf{X} ; $|x|$: the magnitude of the complex scalar x ; $|\mathcal{S}|$: the cardinality of set \mathcal{S} ; $\mathcal{CN}(\cdot, \cdot)$: the circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. System Setup

The considered system consists of an AP with a set $\mathcal{M} \triangleq \{1, \dots, M\}$ of antennas and an IRS with a set $\mathcal{N} \triangleq \{1, \dots, N\}$ of passive reflecting elements that synergistically serve a set $\mathcal{K} \triangleq \{1, \dots, K\}$ of single-antenna UTs, as shown in Fig. 1a. We assume a time-slotted transmission frame structure, i.e., a sequence of T_f timeslots, $\mathcal{T} \triangleq \{1, \dots, T_f\}$, with duration of T seconds each. Throughout the paper, we address the members of these sets via the indexes $m \in \mathcal{M}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$, $k, i \in \mathcal{K}$, and $t \in \mathcal{T}$, unless it is explicitly indicated otherwise.

B. System Operation Modes

The operation modes of the system are depicted in Fig. 1b. When the UTs adopt the TS-SWIPT protocol (modes I and III), timeslot t is divided into a WPT and a wireless information transfer (WIT) sub-slot with duration $T_{\text{WPT}}(t) = (1 - \tau(t))T$ and $T_{\text{WIT}}(t) = \tau(t)T$, where they respectively operate in EH and ID state, i.e., $T_{\text{EH},k}(t) = T_{\text{WPT}}(t)$ and $T_{\text{ID},k}(t) = T_{\text{WIT}}(t)$. The parameter $\tau(t) \in (0, 1)$ denotes the UTs' TS ratio. In modes I and II, the IRS applies the TS-SWIPT scheme as well. Specifically, in modes I.A and II, it operates in EH and reflection (REF) state in the WPT and the WIT sub-slot, respectively, i.e., $T_{\text{EH}}(t) = T_{\text{WPT}}(t)$ and $T_{\text{REF}}(t) = T_{\text{WIT}}(t)$. In modes I.B and I.C, the IRS divides the WPT or WIT sub-slot, respectively, into EH and REF mini-slots with respective duration $T_{\text{EH}}(t) = (1 - \tau(t))(1 - \delta(t))T$ and $T_{\text{REF}}^{(1)}(t) = (1 - \tau(t))\delta(t)T$ in the former case and $T_{\text{EH}}^{(2)}(t) = (1 - \delta(t))\tau(t)T$ and $T_{\text{REF}}(t) = \delta(t)\tau(t)T$ in the latter one, where $\delta(t) \in (0, 1)$, while it operates in REF or EH state in the WIT or WPT sub-slot, respectively, i.e., $T_{\text{REF}}^{(2)}(t) = T_{\text{WIT}}(t)$ in mode I.B and $T_{\text{EH}}^{(1)}(t) = T_{\text{WPT}}(t)$ in mode I.C.

When the PS-SWIPT scheme is utilized by the UTs (modes II and IV) or by the IRS (modes III and IV), we have $T_{\text{EH},k}(t) = T_{\text{ID},k}(t) = T$ and $T_{\text{EH}}(t) = T_{\text{REF}}(t) = T$, respectively.

C. Transmit Sum-Power

In mode IV (PS mode), the AP transmits in timeslot t a signal $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ given by $\mathbf{x}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_k(t) s_k(t)$, where $\mathbf{w}_k(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $s_k(t) \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ denote the TP vector and transmitted symbol assigned to user k , respectively. Therefore, the transmit sum-power is written as

$$P_S(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{w}_k(t)\|^2. \quad (1)$$

In modes I.A, II, and III where the IRS or/and the UTs utilize the TS-SWIPT strategy, the AP transmits in each sub-slot of timeslot t a different signal $\mathbf{x}^{(j)}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$, $j \in \mathcal{J} \triangleq \{1, 2\}$, to balance the EH and QoS requirements, respectively, of these nodes. Specifically, in mode II where the UTs adopt the PS-SWIPT protocol, we have $\mathbf{x}^{(j)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^{(j)}(t) s_k(t)$, where $\mathbf{w}_k^{(j)}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ are the TP vectors assigned to user k in the WPT and WIT sub-slots ($j = 1$ and $j = 2$, respectively). In modes I.A and III where they apply the TS-SWIPT scheme, we have $\mathbf{x}^{(j)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^{(j)}(t) s_k^{(j)}(t)$, where $s_k^{(1)}(t)$ is a pseudorandom energy-carrying signal with unit variance that is drawn from an arbitrary distribution while $s_k^{(2)}(t) \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ refers to an information-bearing signal. Hence, in all cases, the transmit sum-power in each sub-slot is given by

$$P_S^{(j)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(j)}(t) \right\|^2. \quad (2)$$

Likewise, in mode I.B, the transmitted signals in the EH and REF mini-slot of the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t are given by $\mathbf{x}_E^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) s_k^{(1)}(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}_R^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(1)}(t) s_k^{(1)}(t)$, while in the WIT sub-slot of the same timeslot we have $\mathbf{x}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) s_k^{(2)}(t)$. Thus, the transmit sum-power is expressed as

$$P_{S,E}^{(1)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2, \quad P_{S,R}^{(1)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2, \quad P_S^{(2)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2. \quad (3)$$

Finally, in mode I.C, the transmitted signal in the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t is written as $\mathbf{x}^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) s_k^{(1)}(t)$, whereas in the EH and REF mini-slot of the WIT sub-slot of the same timeslot we have $\mathbf{x}_E^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) s_k^{(2)}(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}_R^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) s_k^{(2)}(t)$, respectively. Hence, the transmit sum-power is given by

$$P_S^{(1)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2, \quad P_{S,E}^{(2)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2, \quad P_{S,R}^{(2)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2. \quad (4)$$

D. Reflect Beamforming Matrix

The RB matrix in timeslot t , $\Theta(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$, is expressed as $\Theta = \text{diag}(v_1(t), \dots, v_N(t))$, in general, where $v_n(t) = \beta_n(t)e^{j\theta_n(t)}$ is the reflection coefficient of the n -th IRS element, $\beta_n(t) \in [0, 1]$ stands for its reflection amplitude, and $\theta_n(t) \in [0, 2\pi)$ represents its phase shift.

Specifically, when the IRS utilizes the TS-SWIPT strategy, we assume for ease of practical implementation [25] and without loss of generality [26] that $\beta_n(t) = 0$ (full absorption) and $\beta_n(t) = 1$ (full reflection) in the EH and REF state, respectively, $\forall n, t$. Hence, $\Theta(t) = \text{diag}(e^{j\theta_1(t)}, \dots, e^{j\theta_N(t)})$. On the other hand, when it adopts the PS-SWIPT protocol, we assume for practical convenience and without loss of generality [21] that $\beta_n(t) = \beta(t)$, $\forall n, t$, such that we can control the portion of the incident RF signal's power that is harvested by the IRS by simply adjusting $\beta(t)$. Thus, the RB matrix in this case is given by $\tilde{\Theta}(t) = \text{diag}(\beta(t)e^{j\theta_1(t)}, \dots, \beta(t)e^{j\theta_N(t)}) = \beta(t)\Theta(t)$.

E. Channels

We assume quasi-static, flat-fading channels. The incident AP-IRS, direct AP-UT k , and reflected IRS-UT k baseband equivalent channels in timeslot t are denoted by $\mathbf{G}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, $\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$, and $\mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, respectively.

Depending on whether the IRS applies the TS- or the PS-SWIPT scheme, the effective AP-UT k baseband equivalent channels, $\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \in \mathbb{C}^M$, are respectively expressed as $\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger(t)\Theta(t)\mathbf{G}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger(t)\tilde{\Theta}(t)\mathbf{G}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger(t)\Theta(t)\mathbf{G}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t)$, where $\mathbf{H}_k(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$ are defined as $\mathbf{H}_k(t) \triangleq \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger(t))\mathbf{G}(t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t) \triangleq \text{Diag}(\Theta(t)^*)$.

Note that in modes III and I.B, different RB matrices $\tilde{\Theta}^{(j)}(t)$ and $\Theta^{(j)}(t)$ are used in the WPT sub-slot or in its REF mini-slot ($j = 1$) and in the WIT sub-slot ($j = 2$), respectively, thereby resulting in different effective AP-UT k baseband equivalent channels $(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(j)}(t))^\dagger$ and $(\mathbf{h}_k^{(j)}(t))^\dagger$ as well.

F. EH Model

According to the nonlinear logistic EH model, the harvested DC power $P_k(t)$ at the output of user's k EHR in timeslot t and the RF power $P_{\text{in},k}(t)$ at its input are related as [24]

$$P_k(t) = F(P_{\text{in},k}(t)) = \frac{\Phi(P_{\text{in},k}(t)) - P_{\text{sat},k}\Omega_k}{1 - \Omega_k}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\Phi(P_{\text{in},k}(t)) = \frac{P_{\text{sat},k}}{1 + e^{-a_k(P_{\text{in},k}(t) - b_k)}}, \quad \Omega_k = \frac{1}{1 + e^{a_k b_k}}, \quad (5b)$$

where $F(\cdot)$ refers to a nonlinear function, $\Phi(\cdot)$ represents the logistic function, $P_{\text{sat},k}$ corresponds to the maximum harvested power when the EH circuit is saturated, and a_k and b_k are constants that capture the electrical characteristics of the EH circuit (e.g., resistance, capacitance, etc.). The circuit-dependent parameters $\{P_{\text{sat},k}, a_k, b_k\}$ can be easily obtained via standard curve-fitting tools. The above discussion applies to the IRS as well by dropping the user index k .

G. Users' QoS Constraints

The signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR) of user k in timeslot t should be at least equal to a minimum target, i.e., $\text{SINR}_k(t) \geq \Gamma_k$. Moreover, its data rate (in bits/second) should not exceed a maximum value, i.e., $R_k(t) = W \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k(t)) \leq R_{\text{max},k} \Leftrightarrow \text{SINR}_k(t) \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1$, where W denotes the transmission bandwidth. Under this context, its harvested energy $E_k(t)$ suffices to be at least equal to its maximum possible energy consumption $E_{C,k}^{\text{max}}(t)$ to support the device's operation, i.e., $E_k(t) = T_{\text{EH},k}(t)P_k(t) = T_{\text{EH},k}(t)F(P_{\text{in},k}(t)) \geq E_{C,k}^{\text{max}}(t) = T_{\text{ID},k}(t)(P_{\text{cir},k} + P_{\text{dec},k}^{\text{max}})$, where $P_{\text{cir},k}$ is the fixed power consumption of the front-end circuit, $P_{\text{dec},k}^{\text{max}} = c_k R_{\text{max},k}$ refers to the maximum possible power consumption attributed to the decoding operation, and $c_k > 0$ denotes the EE of the decoder (in Joules/bit) [27]. Since the nonlinear EH function $F(\cdot)$ is monotonically-increasing and, therefore, invertible, we obtain

$$P_{\text{in},k}(t) \geq F^{-1}\left(\frac{E_{C,k}^{\text{max}}(t)}{T_{\text{EH},k}(t)}\right). \quad (6)$$

H. IRS's Battery Dynamics and Energy Requirements

The DC energy harvested by the IRS in timeslot t , $E(t)$, becomes available for consumption in the next timeslot. Let $E_C(t)$ and $B(t)$ represent the energy consumed by the IRS and its battery level, respectively, in timeslot t . Then, the battery dynamics are given by

$$B(t+1) = \min\{B_{\text{max}}, [B(t) - E_C(t)]^+ + E(t)\}, \quad (7)$$

where B_{max} denotes the capacity of the battery and $x^+ = \max\{0, x\}$.

The power consumption of each passive reflecting element in EH state is negligible, while that associated with the REF state equals μ . In order to ensure that the stored energy is not depleted, the consumed energy should not exceed it, i.e., $E_C(t) = T_{\text{REF}}(t)N\mu \leq B(t)$. Additionally, the

maximum harvested energy in timeslot t is limited by the level and capacity of the battery, i.e., $E(t) = T_{\text{EH}}(t)P(t) = T_{\text{EH}}F(P_{\text{in}}(t)) \leq E_{\text{max}}(t) \triangleq B_{\text{max}} - B(t)$. That is,

$$P_{\text{in}}(t) \leq F^{-1}\left(\frac{E_{\text{max}}(t)}{T_{\text{EH}}(t)}\right). \quad (8)$$

Note that the IRS should share its current battery level with the AP to guide resource allocation.

I. Mode IA

The incident signal at the IRS in the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t , $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, and the received signal at user k in the same sub-slot are given by $\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{x}^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)s_k^{(1)}(t)$ and $y_k^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{x}^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t)\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t)s_i^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t)$, respectively, where $n_k(t) \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_k^2)$ denotes the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at user k . Therefore, by ignoring the negligible noise power in the latter case, the RF power at the input of the respective nodes' EHR is written as

$$P_{\text{in}}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2, \quad P_{\text{in},k}(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2. \quad (9)$$

The received signal at user k in the WIT sub-slot of timeslot t after RF-to-baseband conversion is expressed as $y_k^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t)\mathbf{x}^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t)\mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t)s_i^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t)$, where $z_k(t) \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{C,k}^2)$ stands for the RF-to-baseband conversion noise. Thus, by denoting $N_k \triangleq \sigma_k^2 + \sigma_{C,k}^2$ for convenience, the SINR of user k is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t)\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t)\mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k}. \quad (10)$$

J. Mode IB

The incident signal at the IRS in the EH mini-slot of the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t , $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is given by $\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{x}_E^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t)s_k^{(1)}(t)$. Therefore, the RF power at the input of IRS's EH circuit is expressed as

$$P_{\text{in}}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2. \quad (11)$$

Likewise, the received signals at user k in the EH and REF min-slots of the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t are written as $y_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{x}_E^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t)\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_{E,i}^{(1)}(t)s_i^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t)$ and $y_{R,k}^{(1)}(t) = \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{x}_R^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t) = \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}(t)\right)^\dagger \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(1)}(t)s_i^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t)$, respectively.

Hence, by ignoring the negligible AWGN power, the RF power at the input of the EHR is respectively given by

$$P_{\text{in},k}^{(\text{E})}(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{\text{E},i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2, \quad P_{\text{in},k}^{(\text{R})}(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_{\text{R},i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2. \quad (12)$$

The received signal at user k in the WIT sub-slot of timeslot t after RF-to-baseband conversion is expressed as $y_k^{(2)}(t) = \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{x}^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) s_i^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t)$. Thus, the SINR of user k is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k(t) = \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k}. \quad (13)$$

K. Mode I.C

The RF power at the input of IRS's and UT's k EHR in the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t , $P_{\text{in}}^{(1)}(t)$ and $P_{\text{in},k}(t)$, respectively, is given by the right-hand-side (RHS) of Eq. (9). The incident signal at the IRS in the EH mini-slot of the WIT sub-slot of timeslot t , $\mathbf{y}^{(2)}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is written as $\mathbf{y}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{x}_{\text{E}}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_{\text{E},k}^{(2)}(t) s_k^{(2)}(t)$. Therefore, the RF power at the input of IRS's EHR is expressed as

$$P_{\text{in}}^{(2)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_{\text{E},k} \right\|^2. \quad (14)$$

The received signals at user k in the EH and REF mini-slots of the WIT sub-slot of timeslot t after RF-to-baseband conversion are given by $y_{\text{E},k}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{x}_{\text{E}}^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_{\text{E},i}^{(2)}(t) s_i^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t)$ and

$$y_{\text{R},k}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{x}_{\text{R}}^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t) = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_{\text{R},i}^{(2)}(t) s_i^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t),$$

respectively. Thus, the SINR of user k in these mini-slots is written as

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{E},k}(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{\text{E},k}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{\text{E},i}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k}, \quad (15a)$$

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{R},k}(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{\text{R},k}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{\text{R},i}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k}. \quad (15b)$$

L. Mode II

The incident signal at the IRS in the EH sub-slot of timeslot t , $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is given by $\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{x}^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) s_k(t)$. Hence, the RF power at the input of IRS's EHR, $P_{\text{in}}(t)$, is given by the RHS of Eq. (9).

The received signals at user k in the EH and REF sub-slots of timeslot t are written as $y_k^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{x}(t) + n_k(t) = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) s_i(t) + n_k(t)$ and $y_k^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t)\mathbf{x}(t) + n_k(t) = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) s_i(t) + n_k(t)$, respectively. Thus, the corresponding signals at the EH branch are expressed as $y_{\text{E},k}^{(j)}(t) = \sqrt{1 - \rho_k(t)} y_k^{(j)}(t)$ while these at the ID branch (after RF-to-baseband conversion) are given by $y_{\text{I},k}^{(j)}(t) = \sqrt{\rho_k(t)} y_k^{(j)}(t) + z_k(t)$, where $\rho_k(t) \in (0, 1)$ denotes the PS ratio of user k . Therefore, by ignoring the negligible AWGN power, the RF power at the input of the EHR is respectively given by

$$P_{\text{in},k}^{(1)}(t) = (1 - \rho_k(t)) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2, \quad P_{\text{in},k}^{(2)}(t) = (1 - \rho_k(t)) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2. \quad (16)$$

Furthermore, the SINR of user k is respectively expressed as

$$\text{SINR}_k^{(1)}(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 + Z(\rho_k(t))}, \quad (17a)$$

$$\text{SINR}_k^{(2)}(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + Z(\rho_k(t))}, \quad (17b)$$

where we have defined $Z(\rho_k(t)) \triangleq \sigma_k^2 + \frac{\sigma_{\text{C},k}^2}{\rho_k(t)}$ for convenience.

M. Mode III

The input RF signal to IRS's EHR in the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t , $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}^{(1)}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is written as $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}^{(1)}(t) = (1 - \beta(t)) \mathbf{y}^{(1)}(t)$, where $\mathbf{y}^{(1)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) s_k^{(1)}(t)$ is the incident signal at the IRS in this sub-slot. Thus, the input RF power is expressed as

$$P_{\text{in}}^{(1)}(t) = (1 - \beta(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2. \quad (18)$$

The incident signal at the IRS in the WIT sub-slot of timeslot t , $\mathbf{y}^{(2)}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is given by $\mathbf{y}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{x}^{(2)}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) s_k^{(2)}(t)$. Hence, the input RF signal to IRS's EHR is written as $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}^{(2)}(t) = (1 - \beta(t)) \mathbf{y}^{(2)}(t)$ and its power is expressed as

$$P_{\text{in}}^{(2)}(t) = (1 - \beta(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2. \quad (19)$$

The received signal at user k in the WPT sub-slot of timeslot t is given by $y_k^{(1)}(t) = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(1)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{x}^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t) = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(1)}(t)\right)^\dagger \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) s_i^{(1)}(t) + n_k(t)$. Thus, by ignoring the negligible AWGN power, the RF power at the input of its EHR is written as

$$P_{\text{in},k}(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(1)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2. \quad (20)$$

The received signal at user k in the WIT sub-slot of timeslot t after RF-to-baseband conversion is expressed as $y_k^{(2)}(t) = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{x}^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t) = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t)\right)^\dagger \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) s_i^{(2)}(t) + n_k(t) + z_k(t)$. Hence, the SINR of user k is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k(t) = \frac{\left| \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k}. \quad (21)$$

N. Mode IV

The incident signal at the IRS in timeslot t , $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is given by $\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_k(t) s_k(t)$. Therefore, the RF input to its EHR is written as $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}(t) = (1 - \beta(t)) \mathbf{y}(t)$ and its power is expressed as

$$P_{\text{in}}(t) = (1 - \beta(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} |\mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{w}_k(t)|^2. \quad (22)$$

The received signal at user k in timeslot t is given by

$$y_k(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{x}(t) + n_k(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{w}_i(t) s_i(t) + n_k(t).$$

Hence, the signal at the EH branch of user k is written as $y_{\text{E},k}(t) = \sqrt{1 - \rho_k(t)} y_k(t)$ and, by ignoring the negligible AWGN power, the RF power at the input of the EHR is expressed as

$$P_{\text{in},k}(t) = (1 - \rho_k(t)) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2. \quad (23)$$

Likewise, the signal at the ID branch of user k after RF-to-baseband conversion is given by $y_{\text{I},k}(t) = \sqrt{\rho_k(t)} y_k(t) + z_k(t)$. Thus, the SINR of that user is written as

$$\text{SINR}_k(t) = \frac{\left| \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 + Z(\rho_k(t))}. \quad (24)$$

III. PROBLEM FORMULATIONS AND PROPOSED DESIGNS

A. Mode I.A

In principle, we have to optimize in the WPT and WIT sub-slot of timeslot t the variables $\left\{ \left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\}, \tau(t) \right\}$ and $\left\{ \left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\}, \tau(t), \boldsymbol{\theta}(t) \right\}$, such that $P_S^{(1)}(t)$ and $P_S^{(2)}(t)$ are minimized, respectively. We note that $\tau(t)$ is involved in both optimization problems. This motivates us to formulate a corresponding MOP as follows:

$$(P1): \text{O1: } \min_{\left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\}, \left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\}, \tau(t), \boldsymbol{\theta}(t)} P_S^{(1)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \quad (25a)$$

$$\text{O2: } \min_{\left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\}, \left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\}, \tau(t), \boldsymbol{\theta}(t)} P_S^{(2)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \quad (25b)$$

$$\text{s.t. C1: } \text{SINR}_k(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (25c)$$

$$\text{C2: } \text{SINR}_k(t) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (25d)$$

$$\text{C3: } P_{\text{in},k}(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{E_{C,k}^{\max}(t)}{T_{\text{EH},k}(t)} \right) = F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + P_{\text{dec},k}^{\max})}{1 - \tau(t)} \right), \quad (25e)$$

$$\text{C4: } P_{\text{in}}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{E_{\max}(t)}{T_{\text{EH}}(t)} \right) = F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T} \right), \quad (25f)$$

$$\text{C5: } E_C(t) = T_{\text{REF}}(t) N \mu = \tau(t) T N \mu \leq B(t), \quad \text{C6: } 0 \leq \tau(t) \leq 1, \quad \text{C7: } |[\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)]_n| = 1. \quad (25g)$$

C3 motivates us to drop $\tau(t)$ from the optimization variables and vary it instead in $[0, 1]$ with step S , i.e., $\tau(t) \in \mathcal{S} \triangleq \{\tilde{\tau}_1(t), \dots, \tilde{\tau}_{|S|}(t)\}$. We convert the resulting MOP for a fixed value $\tau(t) = \tilde{\tau}_l(t) \in \mathcal{S}$, $l \in \mathcal{L} \triangleq \{1, \dots, |S|\}$, that satisfies C5 to an equivalent SOP by replacing the objective function O2 with the constraint C8, where $\epsilon > 0$ is an arbitrary transmit power budget:

$$(P2): \min_{\left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\}, \left\{ \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\}, \boldsymbol{\theta}(t)} P_S^{(1)}(t) \text{ s.t. C1–C4, C7, C8: } P_S^{(2)}(t) \leq \epsilon. \quad (26)$$

To tackle this challenging non-convex optimization problem, we develop an AM algorithm. Specifically, for fixed $\theta(t)$, (P2) is reduced to the following non-convex optimization task:

$$(P3): \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}} P_S^{(1)}(t) \text{ s.t. C1–C4, C8.} \quad (27)$$

To solve (P3), we apply SDR, i.e., we define the rank-one PSD matrix variables $\mathbf{W}_k^{(j)}(t) \in \mathbb{H}^M$ as $\mathbf{W}_k^{(j)}(t) \triangleq \mathbf{w}_k^{(j)}(t) \left(\mathbf{w}_k^{(j)}(t) \right)^\dagger$ and drop the non-convex rank constraints to obtain:

$$(P4): \min_{\{\mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t)\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \quad (28a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C1}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (28b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C2}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max, k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (28c)$$

$$\overline{\text{C3}}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d, k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d, k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(1)}(t) \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir}, k} + c_k R_{\max, k})}{1 - \tau(t)} \right), \quad (28d)$$

$$\overline{\text{C4}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T} \right), \quad (28e)$$

$$\overline{\text{C5}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon, \quad \overline{\text{C6}}: \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \overline{\text{C7}}: \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (28f)$$

(P4) is a convex semi-definite program (SDP), which can be solved in polynomial time by convex optimization software that applies interior-point methods, such as CVX [28], to obtain $\{\mathbf{W}_k^{(j), l}(t)\}$. If $\text{Rank} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(j), l}(t) \right) = 1$, we can recover the optimal TP vectors of (P3), since then $\mathbf{W}_k^{(j), l}(t) = \mathbf{w}_k^{(j), l}(t) \left(\mathbf{w}_k^{(j), l}(t) \right)^\dagger$; otherwise, we construct rank-one approximations of them, e.g., via eigen-decomposition or Gaussian randomization (GR) [29].

With fixed TP vectors and TS ratio, we formulate the following feasibility-check problem for optimizing the RB vector:

$$(P5): \text{Find } \theta(t) \quad (29a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{C1}: \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d, k}^\dagger(t) + \theta^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d, k}^\dagger(t) + \theta^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (29b)$$

$$\text{C2: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (29c)$$

$$\text{C7: } |[\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)]_n| = 1. \quad (29d)$$

Let $a_{k,i}(t) \triangleq \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t)$ and $\bar{N} \triangleq N + 1$. We also define $\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N}}$, $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^N$, $\Phi_{k,i}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$, and $\mathbf{V}(t) \in \mathbb{H}^{\bar{N}}$ as $\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(t) \triangleq [\boldsymbol{\theta}(t); x]$, $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t) \triangleq \mathbf{H}_k(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t)$, $\Phi_{k,i}(t) \triangleq [\mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{a}_{k,i}^\dagger(t), \mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t) a_{k,i}^*(t); \mathbf{a}_{k,i}^\dagger(t) a_{k,i}(t), 0]$, and $\mathbf{V}(t) \triangleq \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(t) \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^\dagger(t)$, respectively, where x is an auxiliary variable with $|x|^2 = 1$ and $\mathbf{V}(t)$ is a rank-one PSD matrix. Then, we convert (P5) to:

$$\text{(P6): Find } \mathbf{V}(t) \quad (30a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \bar{\text{C8: }} \text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 \geq \Gamma_k \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} (\text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2) + N_k \right), \quad (30b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\text{C9: }} \text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 &\leq \left(2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1 \right) \\ &\times \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} (\text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2) + N_k \right), \end{aligned} \quad (30c)$$

$$\bar{\text{C10: }} |[\mathbf{V}(t)]_{n,n}| = 1, \quad \bar{\text{C11: }} \mathbf{V}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \bar{\text{C12: }} \text{Rank}(\mathbf{V}(t)) = 1. \quad (30d)$$

We could apply the SDR technique to solve (P6). However, the SDR of (P5) is not tight in general. Fortunately and contrary to (P4), we can employ an alternative approach that avoids the inability of GR or similar mechanisms to guarantee a *feasible* rank-one approximation. Specifically, we equivalently express $\bar{\text{C12}}$ as $\bar{\text{C13}}$: $\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_* - \|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_2 \leq 0$, where $\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_* = \sum_j \sigma_j(\mathbf{V}(t)) \geq \|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_2 = \max_j \{\sigma_j(\mathbf{V}(t))\}$ and $\sigma_j(\mathbf{V}(t))$ denotes the j -th singular value of $\mathbf{V}(t)$. Since the equality in $\bar{\text{C13}}$ holds if and only if $\mathbf{V}(t)$ is rank-one, we integrate a penalized version of $\bar{\text{C13}}$ as the objective function of problem (P6). The resulting *implicit* feasibility-check problem under this IA approach takes the following form:

$$\text{(P7): } \min_{\mathbf{V}(t)} p (\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_* - \|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_2) \text{ s.t. } \bar{\text{C8}}\text{--}\bar{\text{C11}}, \quad (31)$$

where $p \gg 1$ is a factor that penalizes the violations of $\bar{\text{C13}}$. (P7) is non-convex, since its objective function consists of the difference of convex (D.C.) functions. Thus, we apply the

SCA technique. In particular, in the $(r + 1)$ -th iteration of the SCA algorithm, we leverage the first-order Taylor approximation

$$\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_2 \geq \|\overline{\mathbf{V}}^{(r)}(t)\|_2 + \text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^1(\overline{\mathbf{V}}^{(r)}(t)) (\boldsymbol{\lambda}^1(\overline{\mathbf{V}}^{(r)}(t)))^\dagger (\mathbf{V}(t) - \overline{\mathbf{V}}^{(r)}(t)) \right) \triangleq \overline{V}^{(r+1)}(t), \quad (32)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{V}}^{(r)}(t)$ denotes the solution obtained in the r -th iteration. Therefore, we recast problem (P7) in the $(r + 1)$ -th iteration as the following convex SDP to obtain $\mathbf{V}^l(t) = \overline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^l(t) (\overline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^l(t))^\dagger$:

$$\text{(P8): } \min_{\mathbf{V}(t)} p \left(\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_* - \overline{V}^{(r+1)}(t) \right) \text{ s.t. } \overline{\text{C8}}\text{--}\overline{\text{C11}}. \quad (33)$$

We solve problems (P4) and (P8) for the given $\tau(t) \in \mathcal{S}$ in an alternating fashion until algorithmic convergence. After spanning \mathcal{S} , we select the feasible value $\tau^*(t) = \tilde{\tau}_{l^*}(t)$ and the corresponding (exact or approximate) TP solutions $\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(j)^*}(t)\} = \{\mathbf{w}_k^{(j),l^*}(t)\}$ and RB solution $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*(t) = \boldsymbol{\theta}^{l^*}(t)$ that provide the minimum objective value in (P3).

Setting ϵ : Prior to solving (P4) and (P8), we have to set ϵ . Note that for fixed $\tau(t) \in \mathcal{S}$, $\epsilon_{\min} = P_{S,\min}^{(2)}(t) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{w}_{k,\min}^{(2)}(t)\|^2$. To compute ϵ_{\min} , we apply the AM framework. Specifically, we initially solve the following optimization problem for fixed $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ to optimize $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$:

$$(\overline{\text{P1}}) : \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}} P_S^{(2)}(t) \text{ s.t. } \text{C1}, \text{C2}. \quad (34)$$

Using SDR, we convert this problem to the following convex SDP:

$$(\overline{\text{P2}}) : \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right) \text{ s.t. } \overline{\text{C1}}, \overline{\text{C2}}, \overline{\text{C7}}. \quad (35)$$

Next, we solve (P5) for fixed $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$ to optimize $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$. This problem is transformed into the convex SDP (P8), as shown earlier. We continue to alternately solve $(\overline{\text{P2}})$ and (P8) until algorithmic convergence to obtain $\{\mathbf{w}_{k,\min}^{(2)}(t)\}$. Then, we let in C8 $\epsilon = \zeta \epsilon_{\min}$, where $\zeta \geq 1$.

The algorithm for optimizing the TP and RB vectors and the TS ratio is presented in Algorithm 1, while Algorithm 2 describes the optimization of the ϵ parameter. In the remaining modes, we omit the optimization of the arbitrary transmit power budgets, which is similar to the procedure described here, as well as the presentation of the algorithms, which are after all implicitly described in the text, due to space constraints.

B. Mode I.B

For each $\tau(t) \in \mathcal{S}$ that satisfies C9: $[(1 - \tau(t)) \delta(t) + \tau(t)] TN\mu \leq B(t)$, we obtain the following SOP using the ϵ -constraint method for fixed $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}(t)$ under the BCD framework:

$$\text{(P9): } \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}, \delta(t)} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t)\|^2 \quad (36a)$$

Algorithm 1 AM Algorithm for mode I.A.

- 1: Initialize $\theta(t)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{V}}(t)$ and obtain $B(t)$.
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: Starting from $l = 1$, set $\tau(t) = \tilde{\tau}_l(t)$, provided that C5 is met; otherwise, set $l = l + 1$ and repeat.
 - 4: **repeat**
 - 5: Solve (P4) with fixed $\theta(t)$ to update $\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)$ and $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$.
 - 6: **repeat**
 - 7: Solve (P8) with fixed $\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)$ and $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$ for given SCA iteration index r to update $\theta(t)$.
 - 8: **until**
 - 9: $(\bar{N} - \lambda^1(\bar{\mathbf{V}}^{(r)}(t))) / \bar{N} \leq \varepsilon > 0$ or the max. number of iterations is reached.
 - 10: **until**
 - 11: The fractional decrease of the objective value in (P3) is below a threshold or the max. number of iterations is reached.
 - 12: **until**
 - 13: The entire set \mathcal{S} has been spanned.
 - 14: **Output:** The value of $\tau(t)$ and the respective TP and RB solutions that provide the minimum objective value in (P3).
-

Algorithm 2 AM Algorithm for setting ϵ in mode I.A.

- 1: Initialize $\theta(t)$, set $\zeta \geq 1$, and obtain $B(t)$.
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: Solve $(\bar{\text{P2}})$ with fixed $\theta(t)$ to update $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$.
 - 4: Solve (P8) for fixed $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$ to update $\theta(t)$.
 - 5: **until**
 - 6: The fractional decrease of the objective value in $(\bar{\text{P1}})$ is below a threshold or the max. number of iterations is reached.
 - 7: **Output:** $\epsilon = \zeta \epsilon_{\min} = \zeta \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{w}_{k,\min}^{(2)}(t)\|^2$.
-

$$\text{s.t. C10: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t)) (1 - \delta(t))} \right), \quad (36b)$$

$$\text{C11: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) (1 - \delta(t)) T} \right), \quad (36c)$$

$$\text{C12: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t)) \delta(t)} \right), \quad (36d)$$

$$\text{C13: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (36e)$$

$$\text{C14: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (36f)$$

$$\text{C15: } 0 \leq \delta(t) \leq 1, \quad \text{C16: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon_1, \quad \text{C17: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon_2. \quad (36g)$$

By applying the SDR method, we obtain the following convex SDP:

$$(P10): \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}, \delta(t)} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) \right) \quad (37a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{C14}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{E,i}^{(1)}(t) \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t)) (1 - \delta(t))} \right), \quad (37b)$$

$$\overline{C15}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}(t)^\dagger \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{W}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) (1 - \delta(t)) T} \right), \quad (37c)$$

$$\overline{C16}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}(t) \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_{R,i}^{(1)}(t) \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t)) \delta(t)} \right), \quad (37d)$$

$$\overline{C17}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (37e)$$

$$\overline{C18}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\mathbf{h}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (37f)$$

$$C15: 0 \leq \delta(t) \leq 1, \quad \overline{C19}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_{R,k}^{(1)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon_1, \quad \overline{C20}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon_2, \quad (37g)$$

$$\overline{C21}: \mathbf{W}_{E,k}^{(1)} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \overline{C22}: \mathbf{W}_{R,k}^{(1)} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \overline{C23}: \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)} \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (37h)$$

Next, with all other variables fixed, we optimize $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t)$ as follows:

$$(P11): \text{Find } \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t) \quad (38a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } C12: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t))^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t)) \delta(t)} \right), \quad (38b)$$

$$C18: \left| [\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t)]_n \right| = 1. \quad (38c)$$

Using the same procedure as in mode I.A and replacing $\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(t)$ and $\mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t)$ by $\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^{(1)}(t)$ and $\mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(1)}(t)$, respectively, we convert (P11) to the following convex SDP:

$$(P12): \min_{\mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t)} p_1 \left(\|\mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t)\|_* - (\bar{V}^{(1)}(t))^{(r+1)} \right) \quad (39a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{C24}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left(\text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,i}^{(1)}(t) \mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t) \right) + \left| a_{k,i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t)) \delta(t)} \right), \quad (39b)$$

$$\overline{C25}: \left| [\mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t)]_{n,n} \right| = 1, \quad \overline{C26}: \mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (39c)$$

We replace $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ by $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$ in (P5) to optimize the latter with the other variables fixed.

C. Mode I.C

For fixed $\tau(t) \in \mathcal{S}$ that satisfies C19: $\delta(t)\tau(t)TN\mu \leq B(t)$, the respective SOP obtained after applying the ϵ -constraint method for fixed $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ under the AM framework takes the form:

$$(P13) : \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t)\}, \delta(t)} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \quad (40a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C20: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t))} \right), \quad (40b)$$

$$\text{C21: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t))T} \right), \quad (40c)$$

$$\text{C22: } \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,i}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (40d)$$

$$\text{C23: } \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,i}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (40e)$$

$$\text{C24: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{(1 - \delta(t))\tau(t)T} \right), \quad (40f)$$

$$\text{C25: } \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (40g)$$

$$\text{C26: } \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (40h)$$

$$\text{C15: } 0 \leq \delta(t) \leq 1, \quad \text{C27: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon_1, \quad \text{C28: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon_2. \quad (40i)$$

By applying the SDR method, we obtain the following convex SDP:

$$(P14) : \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t)\}, \delta(t)} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \quad (41a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C27}}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(1)}(t) \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t))} \right), \quad (41b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C28}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T} \right), \quad (41\text{c})$$

$$\overline{\text{C29}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{E,i}^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (41\text{d})$$

$$\overline{\text{C30}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{E,i}^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (41\text{e})$$

$$\overline{\text{C31}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_{E,k}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \delta(t)) \tau(t) T} \right), \quad (41\text{f})$$

$$\overline{\text{C32}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{R,i}^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (41\text{g})$$

$$\overline{\text{C33}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_{R,i}^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (41\text{h})$$

$$\text{C15}: 0 \leq \delta(t) \leq 1, \quad \overline{\text{C34}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon_1, \quad \overline{\text{C35}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon_2, \quad (41\text{i})$$

$$\overline{\text{C36}}: \mathbf{W}_{E,k}^{(2)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \overline{\text{C37}}: \mathbf{W}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (41\text{j})$$

To optimize $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ with all other variables fixed, we replace $\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)$ by $\mathbf{w}_{R,k}^{(2)}(t)$ in (P5).

D. Mode II

By applying the ϵ -constraint method, we obtain the following SOP for fixed $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ under AM:

$$\text{(P15):} \quad \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \quad (42\text{a})$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \text{C29:} \quad (1 - \rho_k(t)) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k}), \quad (42\text{b})$$

$$\text{C30:} \quad \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (42\text{c})$$

$$\text{C31:} \quad \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (42\text{d})$$

$$\text{C32: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T} \right), \quad (42\text{e})$$

$$\text{C33: } (1 - \rho_k(t)) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k}), \quad (42\text{f})$$

$$\text{C34: } \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (42\text{g})$$

$$\text{C35: } \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (42\text{h})$$

$$\text{C5: } \tau(t) T N \mu \leq B(t), \quad \text{C36: } 0 \leq \tau(t) \leq 1, \quad \text{C37: } 0 \leq \rho_k(t) \leq 1, \quad (42\text{i})$$

$$\text{C8: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon. \quad (42\text{j})$$

By applying the SDR method, we obtain the following convex SDP:

$$\text{(P16): } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \quad (43\text{a})$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C38:}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(1)}(t) \right) \geq \frac{F^{-1} (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (43\text{b})$$

$$\overline{\text{C39:}} \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(1)}(t) \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (43\text{c})$$

$$\overline{\text{C40:}} \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}(t) \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(1)}(t) \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (43\text{d})$$

$$\overline{\text{C41:}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T} \right), \quad (43\text{e})$$

$$\overline{\text{C42:}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) \geq \frac{F^{-1} (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (43\text{f})$$

$$\overline{\text{C43:}} \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (43\text{g})$$

$$\overline{\text{C44:}} \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{h}_k(t) \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (43\text{h})$$

$$\text{C5: } \tau(t)TN\mu \leq B(t), \quad \text{C36: } 0 \leq \tau(t) \leq 1, \quad \text{C37: } 0 \leq \rho_k(t) \leq 1, \quad (43i)$$

$$\overline{\text{C5: }} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon, \quad \overline{\text{C6: }} \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \overline{\text{C7: }} \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (43j)$$

With all other variables fixed, we optimize the RB vector by solving the following problem:

$$\text{(P17): Find } \boldsymbol{\theta}(t) \quad (44a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{C38: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 \geq \frac{F^{-1}(P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (44b)$$

$$\text{C39: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (44c)$$

$$\text{C40: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (44d)$$

$$\text{C7: } |[\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)]_n| = 1. \quad (44e)$$

Using the same definitions as in mode I.A, we obtain, after applying the IA and SCA methods, the following convex SDP:

$$\text{(P18): } \min_{\mathbf{V}(t)} p \left(\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_* - \overline{V}^{(r+1)}(t) \right) \quad (45a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C45: }} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left(\text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2 \right) \geq \frac{F^{-1}(P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (45b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C46: }} \text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 \geq \Gamma_k \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left(\text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2 \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t)) \right), \quad (45c)$$

$$\overline{\text{C47: }} \text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 \leq \left(2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1 \right) \times \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left(\text{Tr}(\Phi_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t)) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2 \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t)) \right), \quad (45d)$$

$$\overline{\text{C10: }} |[\mathbf{V}(t)]_{n,n}| = 1, \quad \overline{\text{C11: }} \mathbf{V}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (45e)$$

E. Mode III

In each timeslot t , it should hold C41: $TN\mu \leq E(t)$. Hence, if this is not the case, we reduce accordingly the number of activated passive reflecting elements in this timeslot to $\tilde{N} = N - \lceil |E(t) - TN\mu| / \mu \rceil$, where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ denotes the ceiling function; otherwise, $\tilde{N} = N$. Notice that this affects the size of the RB matrix and the IRS-reflected channels.

We fix $\beta^{(2)}(t) = 0.5$ and vary, along with $\tau(t)$, $\beta^{(1)}(t)$ in $[0, 1]$ with step B , resulting in purpose in a sparse discrete search space $\mathcal{B}^{(1)}$ to reduce the number of combinations of discrete values of $\beta^{(j)}(t)$ and $\tau(t)$. In this context, after applying the ϵ -constraint method under the BCD framework, we obtain the following SOP for optimizing the TP vectors with fixed RB vectors, $\beta^{(1)}(t) \in \mathcal{B}^{(1)}$, $\beta^{(2)}(t) = 0.5$, and $\tau(t) \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$(P19): \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \quad (46a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C42: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(1)}(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t))^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t))} \right), \quad (46b)$$

$$\text{C43: } (1 - \beta^{(1)}(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T} \right), \quad (46c)$$

$$\text{C44: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(2)}(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t))^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(2)}(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t))^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (46d)$$

$$\text{C45: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(2)}(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t))^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(2)}(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t))^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t) \right|^2 + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (46e)$$

$$\text{C46: } (1 - \beta^{(2)}(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{\tau(t) T} \right), \quad (46f)$$

$$\text{C8: } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\| \mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t) \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon. \quad (46g)$$

By applying the SDR method, we convert (P19) to the following convex SDP:

$$(P20): \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t)\}, \{\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t)\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \quad (47a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C48: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(1)}(t) \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(1)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_i^{(1)}(t) \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{(1 - \tau(t))} \right), \quad (47b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C49}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{(1 - \tau(t)) T (1 - \beta^{(1)}(t))^2} \right), \quad (47c)$$

$$\overline{\text{C50}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (47d)$$

$$\overline{\text{C51}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(2)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{W}_i^{(2)}(t) \right) + N_k} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (47e)$$

$$\overline{\text{C52}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{\tau(t) T (1 - \beta^{(2)}(t))^2} \right), \quad (47f)$$

$$\overline{\text{C5}}: \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \right) \leq \epsilon, \quad \overline{\text{C6}}: \mathbf{W}_k^{(1)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \overline{\text{C7}}: \mathbf{W}_k^{(2)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (47g)$$

We select the feasible values $(\beta^{(1)}(t))^* \in \mathcal{B}^{(1)}$ and $\tau^*(t) \in \mathcal{S}$, along with the respective solutions $(\mathbf{w}_k^{(1)}(t))^*$ and $(\mathbf{w}_k^{(2)}(t))^*$, that provide the minimum objective value in (P19).

The feasibility-check problem for optimizing $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t)$ with all other variables fixed is formulated as follows:

$$\text{(P21): Find } \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t) \quad (48a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C47}}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(1)}(t) \left(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t) \right)^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k})}{(1 - \tau(t))} \right), \quad (48b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C18}}: \left| \left[\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}(t) \right]_n \right| = 1. \quad (48c)$$

Using the same procedure and definitions as in (P11), with the exception that we replace $\mathbf{w}_{R,i}^{(1)}(t)$ by $\mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t)$ and we define $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}^{(1)}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N}}$ as $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}^{(1)}(t) = \beta^{(1)}(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(1)}(t)$, we obtain the following convex SDP:

$$\text{(P22): } \min_{\mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t)} p_1 \left(\left\| \mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t) \right\|_* - \left(\bar{\mathbf{V}}^{(1)}(t) \right)^{(r+1)} \right) \quad (49a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C53}}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left(\text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,i}^{(1)}(t) \mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t) \right) + \left| a_{k,i}^{(1)}(t) \right|^2 \right) \geq F^{-1} \left(\frac{\tau(t) (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k})}{(1 - \tau(t))} \right), \quad (49b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C25}}: \left| \left[\mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t) \right]_{n,n} \right| = 1, \quad \overline{\text{C26}}: \mathbf{V}^{(1)}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (49c)$$

Likewise, in order to optimize $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$ with all other variables fixed, we solve problem (P5) after replacing $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ with $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$ and $\left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t)\right)$ with $\left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta^{(2)}(t) \left(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}(t)\right)^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k(t)\right)$, such that $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t)$ becomes $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}^{(2)}(t) \triangleq \beta^{(2)}(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t)\mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t)$.

F. Mode IV

Since in this mode as well the IRS adopts the PS-SWIPT protocol where $T_{\text{REF}}(t) = T$, C41 should hold, which implies that we accordingly reduce the number of activated IRS elements if required, as in mode III. We vary $\beta(t)$ in $[0, 1]$ with step B and denote the resulting search space as \mathcal{B} . Then, for fixed $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ and $\beta(t) \in \mathcal{B}$, the problem of optimizing the TP vectors and PS ratios under the AM framework is formulated as follows:

$$\text{(P23): } \min_{\{\mathbf{w}_k(t)\}, \{\rho_k(t)\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{w}_k(t)\|^2 \quad (50a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C48: } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 \geq \frac{F^{-1}(P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (50b)$$

$$\text{C49: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (50c)$$

$$\text{C50: } \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t)\boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t)\mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\text{max},k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (50d)$$

$$\text{C51: } (1 - \beta(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} |\mathbf{G}(t)\mathbf{w}_k(t)|^2 \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}} - B(t)}{T} \right), \quad (50e)$$

$$\text{C37: } 0 \leq \rho_k(t) \leq 1. \quad (50f)$$

By applying the SDR method, we obtain the following convex SDP:

$$\text{(P24): } \min_{\{\mathbf{W}_k(t)\}, \{\rho_k(t)\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}_k(t)) \quad (51a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C54:}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k(t) \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i(t) \right) \geq \frac{F^{-1}(P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\text{max},k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (51b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C55:}} \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k(t) \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k(t) \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i(t) \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_k + 1}, \quad (51c)$$

$$\overline{\text{C56}}: \frac{\text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k(t) \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_k(t) \right)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \text{Tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k(t) \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger(t) \mathbf{W}_i(t) \right) + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (51d)$$

$$\overline{\text{C57}}: (1 - \beta(t))^2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{G}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{G}(t) \mathbf{w}_k(t) \right) \leq F^{-1} \left(\frac{B_{\max} - B(t)}{T} \right), \quad (51e)$$

$$\text{C37}: 0 \leq \rho_k(t) \leq 1. \quad (51f)$$

The feasibility-check problem for optimizing $\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$ is formulated in turn as:

$$\text{(P25): Find } \boldsymbol{\theta}(t) \quad (52a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C52}}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t) \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 \geq \frac{F^{-1} (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (52b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C53}}: \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t) \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t) \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \geq \Gamma_k, \quad (52c)$$

$$\overline{\text{C54}}: \frac{\left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t) \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_k(t) \right|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left| \left(\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger(t) + \beta(t) \boldsymbol{\theta}^\dagger(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \right) \mathbf{w}_i(t) \right|^2 + Z_k(\rho_k(t))} \leq 2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1, \quad (52d)$$

$$\text{C7}: |[\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)]_n| = 1. \quad (52e)$$

Using the same procedure and definitions as in (P5), with the exception of $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t)$ which we define as $\mathbf{a}_{k,i}(t) \triangleq \beta(t) \mathbf{H}_k(t) \mathbf{w}_i^{(2)}(t)$, we obtain the following convex SDP:

$$\text{(P26): } \min_{\mathbf{V}(t)} \frac{1}{2p} (\|\mathbf{V}(t)\|_* - \bar{V}^{(r+1)}(t)) \quad (53a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{\text{C58}}: \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t) \right) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 \geq \frac{F^{-1} (P_{\text{cir},k} + c_k R_{\max,k})}{1 - \rho_k(t)}, \quad (53b)$$

$$\overline{\text{C59}}: \text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t) \right) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 \geq \Gamma_k \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} (\text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t) \right) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2) + Z_k(\rho_k(t)) \right), \quad (53c)$$

$$\overline{\text{C60}}: \text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,k}(t) \mathbf{V}(t) \right) + |a_{k,k}(t)|^2 \leq \left(2^{\frac{R_{\max,k}}{W}} - 1 \right) \times \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} (\text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{k,i}(t) \mathbf{V}(t) \right) + |a_{k,i}(t)|^2) + Z_k(\rho_k(t)) \right), \quad (53d)$$

$$\overline{\text{C10}}: |[\mathbf{V}(t)]_{n,n}| = 1, \quad \overline{\text{C11}}: \mathbf{V}(t) \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (53e)$$

TABLE I
ALGORITHMIC COMPLEXITY.

	(P4)	(P8)	(P10)	(P12)	(P14)	(P16)	(P18)	(P20)	(P22)	(P24)	(P26)
m	$3K + 2$	$2K$	$4K + 3$	K	$5K + 4$	$6K + 2$	$3K$	$3K + 3$	K	$3K + 1$	$3K$
n	$2M$	\bar{N}	$3M$	\bar{N}	$3M$	$2M$	\bar{N}	$2M$	\bar{N}	M	\bar{N}

G. Algorithmic Complexity

The interior-point algorithm used by CVX to obtain an ε -optimal solution of the SDPs under study requires at most $\mathcal{O}(I_{\text{it}}I_{\text{SCA}}\sqrt{n}\log(1/\varepsilon))$ iterations, where I_{it} and I_{SCA} denote the number of iterations of the line search and the SCA algorithm, respectively, while n represents the number of optimization variables. The worst-case computation cost per iteration is given by $\mathcal{O}(mn^3 + m^2n^2 + m^3)$, where m refers to the number of SDP constraints [30]. The values of m and n for the different optimization problems are given in Table I.

IV. NUMERICAL EVALUATIONS

In the simulation setup, we have $M = 8$, $N = 64$, $K = 2$. $B_{\text{max}} = 5$ Joules, $\mu = 1.5$ mW, and $W = 1$ MHz. Also, $\Gamma_k = \Gamma = 0$ dB, $\sigma_k^2 = \sigma^2 = -70$ dBm, $\sigma_{C,k}^2 = \sigma_C^2 = -50$ dBm, $a_k = a = 6,400$, $b_k = b = 0.003$, $P_{\text{sat},k} = P_{\text{sat}} = 0.02$ W, $c_k = c = 0.5$ Joules/bit, $P_{\text{cir},k} = P_{\text{cir}} = 0$ dBm, and $R_{\text{max},k} = R_{\text{max}} = 3,900$ bps, $\forall k$. We assume a normalized unit frame duration and consider Rician fading channels with a mean path loss of $C_0 = 30$ dB, a Rician factor of $\kappa = 5$ dB, and a path loss exponent $\alpha_{\text{IRS}} = 2.2$ for the AP-IRS and IRS-UTs channels and $\alpha_{\text{UT}} = 3.6$ for the AP-UTs channels. We focus on the average TSP obtained after 1,000 Monte Carlo simulations. We compare the performance of the proposed schemes with that achieved when the IRS is attached to the power grid (Benchmark 1) and with the case where no IRS is deployed (Benchmark 2). In both scenarios, the UTs adopt the PS-SWIPT protocol.

In all test cases, we notice the following: Benchmarks 1 and 2 achieve the best and the worst performance due to the absence of IRS's EH requirements and coherent RB gains, respectively. The particular performance gap between the conventional IRS implementation and the self-sustainable one is partly due to the low-complexity, yet sub-optimal heuristics used to determine the TS or PS ratios in some scenarios. Modes II and III outperform mode I (TS mode). Mode II provides slightly better performance than mode III, since the optimization of the individual

Fig. 2. Average transmit sum-power vs. (a) UTs' SINR target, (b) UT's maximum allowable rate, (c) IRS's battery capacity, and (d) IRS's number of REs.

PS ratios at the UTs provides better harvested vs. consumed power trade-off and IRS vs. UTs requirements balance. Likewise, mode IV (PS mode) outperforms all other SWIPT variants.

In Fig. 2a, we vary the minimum SINR target of the UTs. The performance gets worse with higher SINR, as expected. We note that mode I.B outperforms mode I.A which, in turn, outperforms mode I.C. This is because more time is allocated to the IRS in assisting the AP in WIT, which compensates for the TSP penalty caused by the smaller time available for harvesting RF energy at the IRS and meeting its EH requirements. In Fig. 2b, we vary the maximum rate requirement of the UTs. The TSP increases with R_{\max} . Higher R_{\max} means that more harvested energy needed for each UT. Thus, mode I.B outperforms mode I.C which, in turn, outperforms mode I.A, since the latter modes do not assist the AP in WET and I.C allocates more time in EH at the IRS than I.A to meet its EH requirements, respectively.

In Fig. 2c, we vary the IRS's battery capacity. For given IRS energy consumption, higher B_{\max} allows us to harvest more energy at the IRS and, therefore, meet its future EH requirements

easier. Therefore, in average, less transmit power is required as B_{\max} increases. Moreover, mode I.C outperforms mode I.A which, in turn, outperforms mode I.B, since more time is allocated in harvesting RF energy at the IRS. This is somewhat compensated from the less time available in assisting the AP in WIT or/and WET to the UTs, which results in a performance penalty. In Fig. 2d, we vary the number of REs. The performance of all modes improves with N up to some point, where the increased power consumption of the IRS dominates the performance over the transmit power savings attributed to the coherent RB gains, thus resulting in performance degradation. Mode I.B presents the worst performance, followed by mode I.A and mode I.C, in that order. These are the modes that are most affected by this turning point in the transmit power savings-IRS power consumption balance as well.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed resource allocation strategies for MISO broadcasting SWIPT systems with batteryless receivers aided by an energy-sustainable IRS. Numerical simulations for the different operation modes highlighted the performance trade-offs attributed to the EH requirements of the IRS.

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